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Summer rainfall and plant height of pulse crops in rice fallows of Northern Kerala

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Abstract

A field study was undertaken to find the effect of rainfall on height of different pulse crops (cowpea, black gram, green gram and red gram) grown in summer fallows of double cropped lowland rice fields under varying nitrogen doses during summer 2018. Height (100 % Recommended Dose of Nitrogen (RDN)) was significantly superior for cowpea. When the effect of rainfall on plant height was studied, the height was comparatively improved when the number of rainy days per week were more than the amount of total rainfall per week. This may have acted as a need-based moisture supply to the crop than the flooding effect caused due to the higher total rainfall in a smaller number of rainy days per week. The results showed that the plant height of pulses was higher in those periods of time when the number of rainy days per week was higher than the total rainfall per week during the course of study. Lesser amounts of rain with a greater number of rainy days per week is better than higher total rainfall per week with lesser number of rainy days per week. Lesser amount of rain with a greater number of rainy days per week acts as need based moisture supply by maintaining the field capacity of the soil where as in the other hand the sudden flooding causes the moisture to be unattainable to the crop and thus it has been reflected in the plant height also. Field capacity maintaining moisture source helps the crop to attain more height which in turn helps in more crop yield. Here, lesser amount of rain with a greater number of rainy days per week gave better performance in plant height.

Keywords: fallow; pulse; lowland, summer; rainfall

Introduction

In northern Kerala, rice-rice-fallow is the major rice-based cropping system, especially in the districts of Kasaragod, Kannur, Kozhikode (John *et al.*, 2014). The greatest challenge in rice cultivation is to make it a remunerative venture by inclusion of different crops in rice-based cropping systems. Utilisation of summer fallows by raising different crops increases system productivity. Pulse crops are potential candidates for considering in summer rice fallows as they fix atmospheric nitrogen and enhance the physical, chemical and biological properties of soil. They are very good sources of protein with low glycaemic index, low gluten and even acts as a functional food (Rao, 2002). The total area under pulses in Kerala during 2015-16 was 3764 ha with a production of 4263 mt and productivity of 1133 kg ha⁻¹ (FIB, 2019). Cultivation of pulses in rice fallows, is the only opportunity for increasing the area and production of pulses. Pulses can be cultivated in summer fallows due to its drought tolerant property which helps it to grow on marginal lands, wastelands, summer fallows of cereals and areas of rainfed agriculture (Adarsh *et al.*, 2019). The short duration helps it to fit in the gap between main crops (FAO, 2016). In this context, an investigation is conducted with an aim to find the effect of the plant height in relation with summer rainfall occurred during the crop period.

Methodology

The field study was undertaken in the double cropped lowland rice fields of Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pilicode, Kerala Agricultural University during summer 2018 (February to May 2018). Cowpea (var. PGCP 6), black gram (var. Co 6), green gram (var. Co. 8) and red gram (var. APK 1) were raised in the field selected for the study. The experimental field is the double cropped lowland rice field located at 12°12'209'' N to 12°15'397'' N latitude and 75°7'025'' E to 75°10'580'' E longitude at an altitude of 6 m above mean sea level. A rainfall of 110.5 mm has been received during experiment of summer fallow crop extended from 24th February to 25th May 2018. During summer crop, the maximum and minimum temperature varied between 33 °C and 34.5 °C and 20.5 °C and 26 °C respectively. The soil of the experimental site, which falls under the order Ultisol, was sandy clay loam in texture, extremely acidic in pH (4.33) and high in available nitrogen (564.48 kg ha⁻¹), available phosphorus (86.76 kg ha⁻¹) and available potassium (371.84 kg ha⁻¹). The experiment was laid out in

Randomised Block Design with twelve treatments and replicated thrice. The treatments were T₁ (cowpea with 100 % recommended dose of nitrogen (RDN)), T₂ (cowpea with 75 % RDN), T₃ (cowpea with 50 % RDN), T₄ (black gram with 100 % RDN), T₅ (black gram with 75 % RDN), T₆ (black gram with 50 % RDN), T₇ (green gram with 100 % RDN), T₈ (green gram with 75 % RDN), T₉ (green gram with 50 % RDN), T₁₀ (red gram with 100 % RDN), T₁₁ (red gram with 75 % RDN), T₁₂ (red gram with 50 % RDN). Cowpea variety PGCP 6 is an early maturing (65-70 days) and was released from Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Uttarakhand. Green gram variety Co 8 with 60 days duration, black gram variety Co 6, red gram variety APK 1 with a duration of 95- 105 days were released from Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore. Rice variety Uma is of medium duration (115-120 days) and was released from Rice Research Station, Moncompu of Kerala Agricultural University. The plot size was 5m x 4m. The crops were raised as per Package of Practices recommendations for crops of Kerala (KAU, 2016) except for red gram as per Regional research Station, Aruppokotai, TNAU. Lime, FYM (farmyard manure), N, P and K, seed rate and spacing at which pulse crops were sown are as per the Package of practice recommendations (KAU, 2016) and for red gram it was given according to TNAU recommendations. The plant height was recorded and mean was worked out. The weather parameters such as average temperature in a week, total rainfall in a week and number of rainy days per week were also worked out.

Results and Discussion

The results showed that the plant height of pulses was higher in those periods of time when the number of rainy days per week was higher than the total rainfall per week during the course of study (Fig. 1 and 2.). Lesser amounts of rain with a greater number of rainy days per week is better than higher total rainfall per week with lesser number of rainy days per week. Lesser amount of rain with more number of rainy days per week acts as need based moisture supply by maintaining the field capacity of the soil where as in the other hand the sudden flooding cause the moisture to be unattainable to the crop and thus it has been reflected in the plant height also (Table 1 and 2).

Conclusion

Field capacity maintaining moisture source helps the crop to attain more height which in turn helps in more crop yield. Here, lesser amount of rain with a greater number of rainy days per week.

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Table 1. Weather Parameters

Max Temp (°C)	Min Temp (°C)	Weekly rainfall (mm)	No. of rainy days per week
32.043	21.5	0	0
32.286	21.5	0	0
32.286	23.071	0	0
32.543	23.786	11.3	2
32.543	23.714	25.6	1
32.429	25.357	0	0
32.829	24.571	4	2
32.429	24.643	1.5	1
33.571	25	4.6	1
33.729	25	0	0
33.771	26	2.6	1
32.786	24.357	14.8	1
32.529	24.929	15.8	3

Table 2. Plant height (cm)

Treatments	Plant height at 4-week stage (cm)	Plant height at 8-week stage (cm)
T ₁ : Cowpea with 100 % N	28.06667	34.73333
T ₂ : Cowpea with 75 % N	25.2	36.2
T ₃ : Cowpea with 50 % N	29.13333	38.73333
T ₄ : Black gram with 100 % N	19.63333	31.73333
T ₅ : Black gram with 75 % N	17.93333	33.2
T ₆ : Black gram with 50 % N	23.83333	34.4
T ₇ : Green gram with 100 % N	22.7	33.8
T ₈ : Green gram with 75 % N	23.66667	32.46667
T ₉ : Green gram with 50 % N	16.7	26.53333
T ₁₀ : Red gram with 100 % N	30.5	79.53333
T ₁₁ : Red gram with 75 % N	28.26667	73.33333
T ₁₂ : Red gram with 50 % N	29.63333	71.33333

Fig. 1. Weather data during summer crop period (February to May 2018)

Fig. 2. Plant height during summer crop period (February to May 2018)